

A pH Metric Study of Some Bivalent Metal Ion—Alizarin S Complexes

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The present communication describes a pH metric study of certain bivalent metal ions VO^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} —Alizarin S systems with a view to determine their stoichiometries and stability constants.

Alizarin and its derivatives are of unusual importance in complexo-metric studies. Many investigators¹⁻⁴ have carried out spectrophotometric studies of Alizarin S complexes of ZrO_2^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{+2} , Pd^{+2} and Th^{+4} ions as regards their stoichiometries and possible use of the ligand in spectrophotometric estimations of the aforesaid metal ions. However, the stabilities of Alizarin S complexes of many metal ions have not been reported so far.

The chemicals employed were all of Analar grade and a Beckman pH meter, model H.2 with glass and calomel electrodes was employed for pH measurements.

The experimental method consisted of pH titrations of the free ligand and mineral acid in the absence of and in the presence of the metal ion being investigated.

The interaction of metal ions with Alizarin S has caused considerable lowering of pH in aqueous solutions and a pH metric titration of 1 : 1 metal-ligand systems with alkali have revealed an inflection at two equivalents of alkali. This obviously indicates that both the phenolic protons of Alizarin S are quite readily liberated consequent to chelate formation.

The required acid dissociation constants of the two phenolic protons of Alizarin S were calculated by an adaptation of Bjerrum's method as followed by Martell *et al.*⁵ and also by Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti⁶ and pK values were found to be in fine agreement (vide Table 1). The literature does not reveal the values pK_1 and pK_2 of Alizarin S for purpose of comparison.

The degree of formation of the metal complexes \bar{n} were calculated from the pH titration curves and it may be mentioned that \bar{n} did not go beyond unity indicating thereby the formation of only 1 : 1 complexes in all the systems except that of Ni^{2+} ion where the formation

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of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes was observed. The stability constants of the metal chelates were calculated from *pH* titration curves by an adaptation of Bjerrum's method as followed by Martell *et al.*⁸ employing the relation

$$n = \frac{1}{c_M} \left[c - \frac{(H^+)^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{(H^+)}{K_1} + 1 \right] A$$

(c_M = total metal ion concentration; c_A = total ligand concentration; A = free ligand concentration; $K_1 K_2$ = Acid dissociation constants of the ligand).

TABLE I

Stability constants of bivalent metal ion—Alizarin S complexes

($pK_1 = 5.85$ and $pK_2 = 10.50$ —Martell's method⁸
 $pK_1 = 5.80$ and $pK_2 = 10.50$ —Rossotti's method⁶
 $\mu = 0.1M$ NaClO₄ T = 25°).

Metal ion M ²⁺	Log K ₁	Log K ₂
VO	13.37	—
UO ₂	12.40	—
Ni	8.90	6.0
Co	8.50	—

It is evident from the data (Table I) that the relative values of the stability constants follows the natural order as proposed by Irving-William's. Co²⁺ < Ni²⁺ < UO₂²⁺ < VO²⁺.

Further details of these investigations will be published subsequently.

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